

The Influence of Service Quality on Library Users at Padang State Polytechnic

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to measure and analyse the influence of service quality on library patrons' satisfaction at Padang State Polytechnic Library. The study is quantitative in nature, utilizing a questionnaire as the data collection instrument. The population and sample utilized are the students of Padang State Polytechnic. Using probability sampling technique, 130 samples were obtained, but the accurate number for use is 100 samples. The data analysis employed is the multiple linear regression analysis method. The research findings indicate that out of the 5 service quality variables used—tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy—3 variables have a significant impact, namely tangible, assurance, and empathy. Meanwhile, reliability and responsiveness show no significance.

KEYWORDS: Service Quality, Library Satisfaction, Library user, Padang State Polytechnic

I. INTRODUCTION

Library is a significantly essential unit within the realm of education, unquestionably necessary for students, scholars, and various groups to support their activities (Aufa & Rahmah, 2013). University libraries play a role as facilities and services that serve as a source of information, knowledge, technology, and culture to enhance the intelligence and quality of students (Kurniawan, 2016). Efforts by universities to produce the best graduates cannot solely stem from the teaching and learning process but also require support from supplementary facilities, one of which is the university library.

The crucial role of university libraries is followed through by Padang State Polytechnic, establishing a library within the campus area serving the entire student body. As a commitment to service, the Padang State Polytechnic library consistently strives to increase its book collection, recording up to 9,479 copies in 2023. Moreover, there have been enhancements to the library's facilities such as tables, chairs, computers, air conditioning, Wi-Fi, and more. However, these efforts have not maximally increased the number of library visitors.

Table 1. Library Visitors Data 2018-2023.

Tahun	Jumlah
2018	1442
2019	4011
2020	2607
2021	2610
2022	2607
2023	2724

Source: State Polytechnic Library of Padang, 2023]

The number of student visits in the last 5 years, from 2018 to 2023 (Table 1), indicates that the average number of visits is only close to half of the total number of students at the Padang State Polytechnic, which amounts to 5,749 individuals. There are several factors contributing to the low level of student visits to the library, one of which is the dissatisfaction of users (individuals utilizing and benefiting from library facilities). One of the reasons is the suboptimal quality of services provided in the library (Hayuni & Nurizzati, 2017).

The objective of this research is to examine the influence of service quality on library user satisfaction. The quality of service provided by the library can be observed in terms of infrastructure as well as the human resources serving there. This study employs five service qualities outlined by Tjiptono (2013), namely a) Physical evidence (tangibles); b)

Reliability; c) Responsiveness; d) Assurance; and e) Empathy. The questions to be addressed are:

1. Do tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy significantly affect the satisfaction of Padang State Polytechnic library users?
2. Which variable has the greater influence?

To ensure clarity and structure, this paper is elaborated in the following manner: First, discussing the research background followed by visitor data, research objectives, and issues. Next, the second section discusses the literature objectives used in this study. Subsequently, the research methodology employed is detailed. This is followed by the discussion and analysis of the obtained results. The article concludes with conclusions and suggestions for future research.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Satisfaction in general, whether as a consumer or potential consumer, can be defined as the feeling of pleasure or disappointment experienced by an individual after comparing the received outcome (performance) with what was expected (expectations) by that individual (Kotler, 2007; Sangadji, 2017). When there is a large gap between them, it signifies a significant dissatisfaction, while a smaller gap indicates greater satisfaction. According to Indrasari (2019), user satisfaction is an individual or group's expectation, a state where someone has successfully acquired what is needed and desired. Additionally, in other literature, the quality of library services is a critical variable in achieving student satisfaction with library utilization.

Service quality can be defined as a dynamic condition related to products, services, human resources, processes, and environments that meet or exceed expectations (Tjiptono, 2013). The influence of service quality on satisfaction is also explained by Samosir (2005), stating that quality service begins with user needs and ends with user responses. User response to service quality is an overall assessment of the excellence of service quality in serving library users. According to Tjiptono (2013), the variable of service quality has indicators that can be divided into 5 models determining service quality: tangibles (physical evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. This study will utilize this model to analyse service quality. Here is an explanation of these five indicators.

a. **Tangibles / Physical Evidence.** Tangibles include the appearance of physical facilities such as the building and room layout, availability of parking, cleanliness, tidiness and comfort of the room, completeness of communication equipment, and the appearance of librarians. In the context of the library, this signifies the physical facilities of the library, layout, and the appearance of librarians.

b. **Reliability** is the ability to provide services as promised. Promised services include providing accurate

information, assisting in problem-solving, and providing reliable service.

c. **Responsiveness.** Responsiveness is the willingness of librarians to assist users and provide quick and responsive service, including readiness to serve, speed in handling transactions, and addressing user complaints.

d. **Assurance.** Assurance includes librarians' knowledge of products (library services and amenities) accurately, the quality of friendliness, attention, and courtesy in providing service, skills in providing information, the ability to provide security, and the ability to instill consumer trust in the company.

e. **Empathy.** Empathy is individual attention given by the institution (in this case, the PNP library) to consumers (users), such as ease of contacting the institution, librarians' ability to communicate with users, and the institution's efforts to understand consumer desires and needs.

Previous empirical studies examining the influence of library service quality have been conducted by Lestari (2020) at the University of Riau library. The study's results indicated that respondents, in this case, the students at the University of Riau, were satisfied with the library service quality there. This study's findings are also consistent with Pandita's research (2017), which showed that the service quality at the Library UPT of Universitas Negeri Makassar falls within a good category.

Measurement of user satisfaction using the LibQUAL+™ method was also carried out at the Semarang Health Polytechnic library (Amalina & Christiani, 2020). This research used samples of students there with variables consisting of Affect of Service (Librarian Performance), Information Control (Information Availability and Access), and Library as Place (Facilities and Infrastructure). The results indicated that in terms of Affect of Service, users were fairly satisfied. Regarding Information Control, users were not quite satisfied, and for Library as Place, users were also not quite satisfied. The service quality from the three LibQUAL+™ aspects at the Semarang Health Polytechnic Library showed a negative Superiority Gap (SG).

Other studies on library service satisfaction have also been conducted by Kalsum, Tarifu, and Ibrahim (2023). They stated that there is a significant influence between service quality and user satisfaction at the Library UPT of Halu Oleo University.

Rahmadani's research (2023) was conducted at the Padang State Polytechnic library but was more specific in measuring satisfaction between users and librarians. Whereas the current author's research will focus more on the five dimensions explained above, which will represent the novelty generated by this research. The results of this study are expected to be used in policymaking for improving library services and contribute to the development of knowledge, particularly related to library services.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study is a quantitative analysis using primary data obtained from the distribution of questionnaires to active students at the Padang State Polytechnic from 2020 to 2022, with a population of 5,749 students. The questionnaires were distributed using Google Forms through the WhatsApp application. The measurement scale used in this study is the Likert scale, structured into indicators as benchmarks for developing instrument items in the form of statements. Each response to an instrument item using the Likert scale has a gradient from very positive to very negative, ranging from Strongly Agree (SA) with a score of 5, Agree (A) with a score of 4, Neutral (N) with a score of 3, Disagree (D) with a score of 2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) with a score of 1.

In this study, probability sampling was used as the sampling technique. Probability Sampling is a sampling technique that gives equal chances for each element or member of the population to be selected as a sample (Sugiyono, 2013).

To answer the first research question, the measurement of service quality, which will later become the independent variable, refers to dimensions outlined according to the concept developed by Tjiptono (2013). The service quality variables consist of five determinants: **tangible**, meaning the availability of physical facilities such as equipment and the appearance of librarians; **reliability**, meaning the ability to provide services as promised; **responsiveness**, meaning the willingness of librarians to help users quickly; **assurance**, meaning knowledge, politeness, and the ability to build customer/user trust; and **empathy**, meaning the willingness to pay attention to users. These five dimensions are then interpreted into 25 questionnaire questions representing each dimension. Meanwhile, the dependent variable, user satisfaction, is interpreted in 8 questionnaire questions representing the experience and alignment of expectations, referring to the measurement concept used by Nasution (2011).

Data processing in this study used SPSS (Statistical Package for The Social Science) version 20. The first step in the data analysis used in this study is to perform descriptive analysis of respondent data who become samples in the study. Then, validity and reliability tests were conducted. According to Priyatno (2018), a validity test is used to measure the validity of a questionnaire by correlating the scores of each variable item, and the significance testing is done using the criteria using the t-table at a significance level of 0.05 with a two-sided test. If the positive value and the calculated $r >$ the table r , the item is considered valid. If the calculated $r <$ the table r , the item is considered not valid. Meanwhile, the reliability test is a continuation of the validity test, where only valid items are tested, and to determine whether the instrument is reliable or not, the limit used is 0.6. According to Sekaran (2017), reliability below 0.6 is not good, 0.7 is acceptable, and above 0.8 is good.

The next step is to determine the coefficient of determination (R^2) to measure how far the model's ability to explain dependent variables. If R^2 equals 0, then there is no percentage of the contribution of the influence given by independent variables to the dependent variable, or the variation of independent variables used in the model does not explain any variation of the dependent variable. Conversely, if R^2 equals 1, then the percentage of the contribution of the influence given by independent variables to the dependent variable is perfect, or the variation of independent variables used in the model explains 100% of the variation of the dependent variable (Priyatno, 2018).

The second research question is answered by performing multiple linear regression analysis with the regression model as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + e$$

Where Y = satisfaction; α = Constant; X_1 = Tangible (Physical Evidence); X_2 = Reliability; X_3 = Responsiveness; X_4 = Assurance; X_5 = Empathy; β = Regression coefficient of each variable; and e = standard error. Multiple regression analysis must meet the classic assumption testing principles of linearity, normality, and no problems of autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity, and multicollinearity.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of the questionnaire distribution identified respondent characteristics based on enrolment years. The majority or the most dominant respondents belonged to the 2020 cohort, comprising 59 respondents out of 100, accounting for 58.7%. The smallest group was the 2022 cohort, with 15 respondents out of 100, making up 14.7%. The rest were from the 2021 cohort (Figure 1). Female respondents were the majority, with 62 out of 100 respondents, making up 61.5% (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Diagram of Respondents based on Enrollment Year and Gender

Source: Self-processed (2023)

Based on the field of study, among the respondents from the Padang State Polytechnic, the most dominant was the Business Administration department, comprising 45 respondents, while the least represented were the English Language and Accounting Departments, each having only 4 respondents (Table 2).

Table 2. Total Responden based on Major

Major	Recipient
Administration Commerce	45
Electrical Engineering	15
English	4
Civil Engineering	14
Accountancy	4
Mechanical Engineering	9
Technology Information	9
Amount	100

Source : processed , 2023

The variables in the study consist of independent variables (X), namely service quality comprising dimensions of tangibles, responsiveness, reliability, assurance, empathy, and dependent variables (Y), which are student satisfaction. The data for these variables were obtained from the distributed questionnaires. For further clarification, please refer to Table 3 below.’

Table 3. Questionnaire Results

Variables / Questions Questionnaire	SA (5)	A (4)	N (3)	D (2)	SD (1)
Quality Service					
<i>Tangibles</i>					
reading room in the library is very comfortable. (X.1)	33	47	18	1	1
Wifi available for free at the library Padang State Polytechnic (X.2)	31	51	16	1	1
Facility complete (tables, chairs) in the library Padang State Polytechnic (X.3)	33	52	12	2	1
Network wifi smooth and fast (X.4)	19	40	33	7	1
Books in the library covers all field knowledge knowledge (X.5)	20	39	31	9	1
<i>Responsiveness</i>					
Librarian know the layout books in the library Padang State Polytechnic (X.6)	18	51	24	6	1
Librarian Professional in serve visitors library (X.7)	12	53	30	4	1
Librarian own reliable capabilities _ in respond visitors library (X.8)	11	53	31	4	1
Librarian capable give instruction as well as capable direct every visitors library (X.9)	13	56	27	3	1
Librarian Ready in help visitors library (X.10)	14	54	26	5	1

<i>Reliability</i>					
Librarian handle complaint visitors library (X.11)	11	51	32	5	1
Librarian initiative give help to visitors library (X.12)	11	39	39	10	1
Librarian have characteristic can trusted (X.13)	11	60	28	0	1
Librarian willing in accept response visitors (X.14)	11	56	30	2	1
Librarian capable give explanation on question from visitors (X.15)	13	64	20	2	1
<i>Assurance</i>					
Librarian behave patient and polite (X.16)	13	54	27	5	1
Atmosphere library secure (X.17)	33	45	19	0	1
Librarian friendly in give explanation (X.18)	12	55	31	1	1
Librarian behave open to visitors (X.19)	16	43	36	4	1
Librarian have ability and knowledge (X.20)	18	57	24	0	1
<i>Empathy</i>					
Librarian serve visitors with completely heart (X.21)	15	53	29	2	1
Librarian intertwine connection Good with visitors library (X.22)	14	59	25	1	1
Librarian give attention to visitors without picky (X.23)	14	55	28	2	1
Librarians and visitors easy in transaction (X.24)	12	53	31	3	1
Librarian understand difficulties experienced _ visitors library (X.25)	13	51	32	3	1
<i>Satisfaction Reader</i>					
Student feel satisfied and happy moment are inside _ library (Y.1)	18	62	16	3	1
Librarian friendly to visiting students (Y.2)	13	55	26	5	1
Completeness books in the library in accordance with expected (Y.3)	14	44	31	8	3
Student easy in look for book (Y.4)	11	46	34	6	3
Facility support in accordance with expected (Y.5)	13	55	29	2	1
Student often visit to library (Y.6)	8	46	41	4	1
Always invite friends For visit to library (Y.7)	9	58	30	2	1
Student own good experience _ after from library (Y.8)	10	55	31	3	1

!A= Strongly Agree, A= Agree, N= Neutral, D= Disagree, SD= Strongly Disagree

From the validity test results of the collected questionnaire data in this study, it can be concluded that all statement items in the questionnaire can be considered valid since the calculated r is greater than the table r. This indicates that all statement items can be used and are valid for this research. Regarding the reliability test results, the Cronbach's Alpha values for variables X and Y, out of the 33 questions in the questionnaire, are deemed reliable as the Cronbach's Alpha values are > 0.6.

Table 4. Results of Validity and Reliability Tests

Variables / Indicators	Validity test			Reliability Test	
	r count	r table	Information	α	Information
Quality Service					
X.1	0.800	0.1966	VALID	0.798	Reliable
X.2	0.787	0.1966	VALID	0.772	Reliable
X.3	0.796	0.1966	VALID	0.779	Reliable
X.4	0.829	0.1966	VALID	0.895	Reliable
X.5	0.751	0.1966	VALID	0.931	Reliable
X.6	0.867	0.1966	VALID	0.844	Reliable
X.7	0.856	0.1966	VALID	0.769	Reliable
X.8	0.855	0.1966	VALID	0.761	Reliable
X.9	0.816	0.1966	VALID	0.75	Reliable
X.10	0.839	0.1966	VALID	0.796	Reliable
X.11	0.839	0.1966	VALID	0.781	Reliable
X.12	0.803	0.1966	VALID	0.856	Reliable
X.13	0.826	0.1966	VALID	0.667	Reliable
X.14	0.826	0.1966	VALID	0.719	Reliable
X.15	0.822	0.1966	VALID	0.697	Reliable
X.16	0.814	0.1966	VALID	0.79	Reliable
X.17	0.776	0.1966	VALID	0.892	Reliable
X.18	0.815	0.1966	VALID	0.712	Reliable
X.19	0.831	0.1966	VALID	0.825	Reliable
X.20	0.802	0.1966	VALID	0.712	Reliable
X.21	0.833	0.1966	VALID	0.756	Reliable
X.22	0.934	0.1966	VALID	0.707	Reliable
X.23	0.869	0.1966	VALID	0.743	Reliable
X5.4	0.898	0.1966	VALID	0.753	Reliable
X5.5	0.842	0.1966	VALID	0.766	Reliable
Satisfaction					
Y1	0.834	0.1966	VALID	0.742	Reliable
Y2	0.832	0.1966	VALID	0.787	Reliable
Y3	0.863	0.1966	VALID	0.934	Reliable
Y4	0.779	0.1966	VALID	0.88	Reliable
Y5	0.777	0.1966	VALID	0.737	Reliable
Y6	0.751	0.1966	VALID	0.743	Reliable
Y7	0.768	0.1966	VALID	0.697	Reliable
Y8	0.788	0.1966	VALID	0.732	Reliable

Results from assumption tests classic namely the normality test for determine whether the data obtained follow normal distribution can see in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Normal probability Plot
Source: SPSS, 2023

Figure 2 shows that in the Normal Probability Plot, the data scatter around the diagonal line and follow its direction, indicating a normal distribution pattern. Hence, it can be concluded that the normality assumption has been met.

The multicollinearity test aims to determine the level of correlation between independent variables. There is no multicollinearity issue if the tolerance value is > 0.100 and the VIF value is < 10.00 . From the results in Table 5, it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity issue since the tolerance values for each variable are > 0.10 , and the VIF values are less than 10.00, indicating the absence of multicollinearity.

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	,896	1,621		,553	,582		
	Tangibles	,339	,101	,224	3,349	,001	,510	1,961
	Reliability	-,187	,140	-,124	-1,342	,183	,265	3,779
	Responsiveness	,123	,188	,075	,654	,515	,173	5,787
	Assurance	,791	,176	,501	4,506	,000	,184	5,443
	Empathy	,428	,175	,279	2,446	,016	,175	5,712

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction
source : SPSS version 20, 2023

Heteroskedasticity test aims to assess whether there is unequal variance of residuals from one observation to another within a regression model. If the sig value is > 0.05 , there is no heteroskedasticity. However, if $\text{sig} < 0.05$, then heteroskedasticity is present. The heteroskedasticity test results (Table 6) using the Glejser test, as shown in Table 6, indicate the absence of heteroskedasticity as the significant result is > 0.05 .

Table 6. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	,955	1,107		,863	,390
	Quality Service	,011	,012	,094	,935	,352

a. Dependent Variable: Abs.RES
Source : SPSS version 20, 2023

To address the second research question regarding the influence of the independent variable, service quality, on the dependent variable, user satisfaction, in the Politeknik Negeri Padang library, multiple linear regression analysis was conducted. The results of the multiple linear regression test can be seen in Table 7 as follows.

Table 7. Multiple Linear Regression Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	,896	1,621		,553	,582
	Tangibles	,339	,101	,224	3,349	,001
	Reliability	-,187	,140	-,124	-1,342	,183
	Responsiveness	,123	,188	,075	,654	,515
	Assurance	,791	,176	,501	4,506	,000
	Empathy	,428	,175	,279	2,446	,016

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction
Source : SPSS, 2023

Based on Table 7 results of multiple linear regression tests, equation model regression obtained _ as following:

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$$Y = 0.896 + 0.339X_1 - 0.187X_2 + 0.123X_3 + 0.791X_4 + 0.428X_5$$

The constant value (a) is 0.896, indicating that if tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy have a value of 0 or absent, customer satisfaction will be 0.896. The regression coefficient value of the tangible variable (b1) is positive at 0.339, meaning that for every 1 percent increase in the tangible variable, satisfaction also increases by 0.339. The regression coefficient value of the reliability variable (b2) is negative at -0.187, signifying that for every 1 percent increase in the reliability variable, satisfaction decreases by 0.187. The coefficient value of the responsiveness variable (b3) is positive at 0.123, indicating that for every 1 percent increase in the responsiveness variable, satisfaction also increases by 0.123. The coefficient value of the assurance variable is positive at 0.791, signifying that for every 1 percent increase in the assurance variable, satisfaction also increases by 0.791. Lastly, the coefficient value of the empathy variable is positive at 0.428, meaning that for every 1 percent increase in the empathy variable, satisfaction also increases by 0.428.

The service quality at the Padang State Polytechnic library is good, as respondents generally agreed with all indicators proposed in the questions. Based on the questionnaire scores, respondents agreed that the library reading space is very comfortable, Wi-Fi is freely available, facilities are complete with tables, chairs, and others, and librarians can easily locate books, aiding students in finding required information. Librarians are trustworthy, understand student complaints, and are ready to assist with any issues within the library. Overall, students (respondents) are satisfied with the service, although some respondents expressed dissatisfaction with a few indicators that didn't meet their expectations. This indicates that satisfaction is provided by the library, encompassing comfort while in the library, enjoyment, the completeness of required books, regular visits to the library, and a positive overall experience after leaving the library.

Answering the second problem statement. Based on the obtained statistical equation, it is evident that the variable with the greatest influence is Assurance (at 0.791). Respondents consider the points within the Assurance indicator to be significantly important (such as a patient librarian, a comfortable library atmosphere, friendly and helpful librarians, and having adequate knowledge and abilities related to the library).

Furthermore, a partial test was conducted with the results in Table 8. It can be concluded that for the tangible variable (X1), the significance value of $0.001 \leq 0.05$ and the t-value of $3.349 \geq t\text{-table of } 1.985$, meaning that the tangible variable has a strong and significant effect on user satisfaction. For the reliability variable (X2), the significance value of $0.183 \geq 0.05$ and the t-value of $-1.342 \leq 1.985$, indicating that the reliability variable does not

affect user satisfaction. The responsiveness variable (X3) has a significance value of $0.515 \geq 0.05$ and a t-value of $0.654 \leq 1.985$, indicating that the responsiveness variable does not affect user satisfaction. Subsequently, the assurance variable (X4) has a significance value of $0.000 \leq 0.05$ and a t-value of $4.506 \geq 1.985$, indicating that the assurance variable has a significant effect on user satisfaction. Lastly, the empathy variable (X5) has a significance value of $0.016 \geq 0.05$ and a t-value of $2.446 \geq 1.985$, signifying that the empathy variable has a significant effect on user satisfaction.

Table 8. t test results

Coefficients ^a Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	,896	1,621		,553	,582
Tangibles	,339	,101	,224	3,349	,001
Reliability	-,187	,140	-,124	-1,342	,183
Responsiveness	,123	,188	,075	,654	,515
Assurance	,791	,176	,501	4,506	,000
Empathy	,428	,175	,279	2,446	,016

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction

Source : SPSS version 20, 2023

The t-test results indicate that the reliability and responsiveness variables do not affect user satisfaction because the t-value is smaller than the t-table value. However, the tangible, assurance, and empathy variables significantly affect user satisfaction as the t-value is greater than the t-table value.

The results from the F-test using SPSS, shown in Table 9, are as follows:

Table 9. F Test Results ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1952,257	5	390,451	69,200	,000 ^b
	Residual	530,383	94	5,642		
	Total	2482,640	99			

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Empty, Tangible, Reliability, Assurance, Responsiveness

Source : SPSS ,2023

Based on the table above, it can be observed that the significance value is $0.000 \leq 0.05$ and the calculated F-value $69.200 \geq$ the tabulated F-value 2.311. Therefore, it can be concluded that tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy variables simultaneously have a significant effect on user satisfaction.

Table 10. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,856 ^a	,734	,731	2,598

a. Predictors: (Constant), Quality service

Source : SPSS version 20, 2023

Based on table 10, the coefficient of determination (R-squared) is 0.731. This means that the independent variable, service quality, can explain 73.1% of the influence on the dependent variable, student satisfaction. Meanwhile, 26.9% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

The research findings conclude that service quality significantly impacts library users' satisfaction. Out of the service quality indicators used, three were influential and significant: tangibles, assurance, and empathy. Meanwhile, the other two indicators, reliability and responsiveness, were found to be insignificant. In the multiple linear regression analysis, all indicators (tangibles, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy) displayed positive values, except for reliability, which had a negative value. Factors related to reliability, such as handling user complaints, providing assistance, responding to inquiries, were perceived by library users as less urgent, as they felt capable of self-service. This perception differed significantly from the other dimensions, which users deemed urgent and essential.

In the F-test results, the variables tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy collectively and simultaneously influenced library users' satisfaction. The coefficient of determination (R²) showed that 73.1% of student satisfaction (Y) was influenced by service quality variables (X), while the remaining 26.9% was affected by other unexamined variables in this study.

Suggestions for future research include enhancing service quality across each dimension, particularly focusing on significant indicators. Moreover, addressing changes in dimensions that have achieved low scores, such as reliability (related to providing assistance to library visitors) and assurance (regarding the openness of librarians towards visitors and the level of security in the library environment). Additionally, future studies could consider including other factors or indicators, such as Technological Availability for access, Psychological and Emotional Factors, and Sustainability and Innovation as new indicators to improve library user satisfaction.

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